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Review Article

Analytical Methods for the Metoprolol Succinate and Empagliflozin in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Cardiovascular diseases and diabetes mellitus represent two of the most significant global health burdens, frequently coexisting and synergistically increasing morbidity and mortality. Metoprolol succinate, a cardioselective β_1 adrenergic receptor blocker, is extensively prescribed for hypertension, angina pectoris, heart failure, and arrhythmias. Empagliflozin, a sodium–glucose co transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitor, is widely used in the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus and has shown remarkable cardiovascular and renal protective effects beyond glycemic control. This review article provides a comprehensive overview of Metoprolol succinate and Empagliflozin, including their pharmacological actions, physicochemical properties, therapeutic applications, and reported analytical methods. Special emphasis is placed on analytical techniques such as UV spectrophotometry, high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC), and liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (LC–MS/MS) used for their estimation individually and in combined dosage forms. This review aims to serve as a ready reference for researchers, analysts, and formulation scientists.

INTRODUCTION

Metoprolol succinate (MET) is an antihypertensive medication that acts as a competitive beta-adrenergic receptor antagonist (Cardio selective). It exhibits membrane stabilizing effects when administered at a higher dose than that required to demonstrate antagonist property. ⁽¹⁾

Mechanism of Action:

Metoprolol is a beta-1-adrenergic receptor inhibitor specific to cardiac cells with negligible effect on beta-2 receptors. This inhibition decreases cardiac output by producing negative chronotropic and inotropic effects without presenting activity towards membrane stabilization nor intrinsic sympathomimetics. ⁽²⁾

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Empagliflozin (EMP) is an inhibitor of sodium-glucose co-transporter-2 (SGLT2), the transporters primarily responsible for the reabsorption of glucose in the kidney. It is used clinically as an adjunct to diet and exercise, often in combination with other drug therapies for the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus.⁽³⁾

Mechanism of Action

The vast majority of glucose filtered through the glomerulus is reabsorbed within the proximal tubule, primarily via SGLT2 (sodium-glucose linked co-transporter-2) which is responsible for ~90% of the total glucose reabsorption within the kidneys. Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase on the basolateral membrane of proximal tubular cells utilize ATP to actively pump Na⁺ ions into the interstitium surrounding the tubule, establishing a Na⁺ gradient within the tubular cell. SGLT2 on the apical membrane of these cells then utilize this gradient to facilitate secondary active co-transport of both Na⁺ and glucose out of the filtrate, thereby reabsorbing glucose back into the blood – inhibiting this co-transport, then, allows for a marked increase in glucosuria and decrease in blood glucose levels. Empagliflozin is a potent inhibitor of renal SGLT2 transporters located in the proximal tubules of the kidneys and works to lower blood glucose levels via an increase in glucosuria.⁽⁴⁾

Figure 1 Structure of Empagliflozin

Metoprolol succinate and **Empagliflozin** treat different conditions, but are often used together for cardiovascular issues like heart failure, diabetes, hypertension, and post-heart attack recovery, as they complement each other's actions.

PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES

Metoprolol succinate is a white, crystalline powder, highly water-soluble, used as a beta-blocker; review articles highlight its poor micromeritic properties (flow, compressibility) and low melting point, leading to extensive research on developing sustained-release (SR) formulations using polymers (like HPMC, Carbopol) or co-crystals to improve solubility, stability, and patient compliance by reducing dosing frequency. Studies use techniques like DSC, FTIR, and XRPD to characterize these improved formulations, focusing on enhancing dissolution and bioavailability.⁽⁵⁾

Empagliflozin is a white to yellowish powder, practically insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents like DMSO and ethanol, with a molecular weight of ~450.91 g/mol, chemical formula C₂₃H₂₇ClO₇, and is a C-glycoside structure, not hygroscopic, and stable without polymorphism, serving as an SGLT2 inhibitor.⁽⁶⁾

Figure 2 Structure of Metoprolol succinate

Table 1 Official method for assessment of Metoprolol succinate

Sr. No.	Official	Description	Ref. No.
01	Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP-2018)	Method : Chromatography Wavelength : 223 nm Stationary phase : Octadecylsilane Silica (15cm x 3.9mm) Mobile phase : Buffer : Acetonitrile (60:40) Flow rate : 0.9 mL/min Detection : Spectrophotometer	7
02	United States Pharmacopoeia (USP-2011)	Method : Potentiometric method Solvent : Anhydrous acetic acid Titrant : 0.1M Perchloric acid 1ml of 0.1M Perchloric acid \approx 32.64mg C ₄ H ₅ 6N ₂ O ₁₀	8
03	British Pharmacopoeia (BP-2018)	Method : Liquid Chromatography Wavelength : 223nm Stationary phase : Octadecylsilyl silica Mobile phase : Sodium dodecyl sulphate : CAN (60: 40) Flow rate : 0.9 mL/min Detection : Spectrophotometer	9

Table 2 Reported methods for assessment of Metoprolol succinate

Sr. No.	Author	Title	Method	Description	Ref. No.
01	Bharad VJ, et al.	Metoprolol succinate	Spectroscopic Method	Solvent: Water, HCl, Methanol λ_{\max} : 222nm Range : 5-25 μ g/ml	10
02	Jain PS, et al.	Metoprolol succinate in bulk and tablet dosage form	UV-spectrophotometric method	Solvent : Water λ_{\max} : 264 nm & 283 nm Range : 40-200 g/ml	11
03	Dhole SM, et al.	Metoprolol succinate and Amlodipine Besylate in Their Combined Tablet Dosage Form	UV Spectrophotometric	Solvent : Methanol and Water λ_{\max} : 221nm (MS) & 364nm(AB) Range: 2-20 μ g/mL (MS) & 1-10 μ g/mL (AB)	12
04	Vora BN, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Olmesartan medoxomil in the tablet dosage form	UV spectrophotometric method	Solvent: Methanol and water λ_{\max} : 221 nm (MS) & 257 nm (OM) Range: 5–25 μ g/ml(M) & 4–20 μ g/ml (O)	13
05	Gopika VC, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Benidipine hydrochloride in their combined tablet dosage form	UV spectrophotometric method	Solvent: Methanol λ_{\max} : 223nm (MS) & 237nm (BH) Range: 3-21 μ g/mL	14
06	Chabukswar AR, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Amlodipine in Their Combined Dosage Form	Absorption Corrected (A) & Isoabsorptive Point (B)	Solvent: Methanol λ_{\max} : 277.017 nm and 235.62 nm Range: 50-250 μ g/ml (M) & 5-25 μ g/ml (A)	15
07	Modi M, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Telmisartan In Combined	1. Derivative simultaneous	Solvent: Methanol λ_{\max} : 230 nm	16

		Pharmaceutical Formulation	<p>equation (Vierodt's method)</p> <p>2. 1st derivative Q-Absorbance equation</p> <p>3. Absorbance correction</p> <p>4. Combination of 1st derivative dual WL</p>	Range: 3-20 µg/ml (METO) & 4-16 µg/ml (TEL)	
08	Patel PB, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Telmisartan and in tablet dosage form	Second order derivative	Solvent: Methanol λ _{max} : 299 nm(T) (ZCP – M) & 224nm (M) (ZCP-T) Range: 3-15µg/ml	17
09	Shanmu gasunda ram V, Et Al.	Metoprolol succinate & Atorvastatin Using Biorelevant Dissolution Media (Fasted State Small Intestinal Fluid)	RP-HPLC	λ _{max} : 244nm Range: 50–250 µg/ml (MS) & 10-50µg/ml (AT) Mobile Phase : Phosphate buffer : Acetonitrile (35:65) Detector : UV detection Flow rate : 1 ml/min Run time : 15.0 min	18
10.	Madhukar A, et al.	Metoprolol succinate in tablet dosage form	RP-HPLC	Solvent: Methanol λ _{max} : 225nm Range : 25-125µg/mL Column : C ₁₈ Detector : PDA Flow rate : 1ml/min Run time : 4.8 min	19
11.	Yska JP, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & α-hydroxy metoprolol in human serum, For application in pharmacokinetics	High- resolution accurate mass LC-MS	Solvent: Methanol Range : 5 - 250 µg/L Mobile Phase : Water: Acetonitrile (15 : 85, v/v) Detector: Exactive® Orbitrap Run time: 15 min	20
12.	Agrawal S, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Trimetazidine Hydrochloride	Simultaneous Estimation using HPTLC	Solvent : n-butanol : Water : Methanol : Ammonia λ _{max} : 213nm Range : 500-2500 ng band ⁻¹ (TH) & 500-2500 ng band ⁻¹ (MS) Mobile Phase : n-butanol : Water : Methanol: Ammonia (8.5 : 0.1 : 0.1: 0.85, v/v) Stationary Phase : Pre-coated silica gel G 60 F254 TLC plate	21
13.	Rao DS, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Cilnidipine Dissolution Test	RP-HPLC	Solvent: OPA: Methanol (70:30) λ _{max} : 285 nm Range: 50% to 150%	22

				Mobile Phase : OPA: Methanol (70 : 30) Column : ELIPSE C ₁₈ Flow rate: 1.0mL/min Run time: 2.59 (M) & 4 min (CD)	
14.	Corina MS, et al	Metoprolol succinate & Bisoprolol	MS, GC coupled with GC, HPLC	-	23
15.	Saravanan G, et al	Metoprolol succinate & Cilnidipine	Stability Indicating RP-HPLC	Solvent: Water : Acetonitrile (50 : 50) λ_{\max} : 230 nm Mobile Phase : Acetonitrile : Sod. Dihydrogen ortho phosphate buffer (65 : 35) Column: STD kromasil 150 C18 Flow rate: 0.8ml/min Run time: 2 min(M)& 3min	24
16.	Kumar CH, et al	Metoprolol succinate	stability indicating RP-HPLC	Solvent: Methanol λ_{\max} : 223 nm Range: 20-200 μ g/ml Mobile Phase : Buffer (PH- 6.8) : Methanol : Acetonitrile (600 : 50 : 350) Detector: PDA Run time: 11 min	25
17.	Sheikh KS, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Telmisartan in extended release tablets	Stress degradation studies by a validated stability indicating RP- HPLC method	Solvent: Methanol λ_{\max} : 222 nm Range: 80–2 μ g/mL (TS) & 100-4 μ g/ mL (MS) Mobile Phase : 0.05 M Sodium dihydrogen Phosphate buffer pH 3.0 : Acetonitrile (75 : 25 v/v) Column: Inertsil ODS 3V Detector: PDA Flow rate: 1ml/min	26
18.	Jain N, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Telmisartan	UV Spectrophotometry & RP- HPLC	Solvent: 50% methanol λ_{\max} : 240.5 nm(MS) and 237.5 nm(TEL) Chromatogram(225nm) Range : 5-25 μ g mL (MS) & 8-40 μ g mL(TEL) Mobile Phase : Methanol: Acetonitrile : Phosphate buffer (pH-5) 35:35:30 v/v/v Column: C ₁₈ Flow rate: 1ml/min	27
19.	Shrivastav PS, et al.	Metoprolol succinate in human plasma	chiral LC- ESI- MS/MS	Range: 0.500-500 ng/mL Mobile Phase : 15 mM Ammonium acetate : Water	28

				: 0.1% (v/v), Diethyl amine : Acetonitrile (50:50) Column: Lux amylose -2 Run time: 7 min	
20.	Kashya p R, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Chlorthalidon in Bulk and Dosage Form	HPLC	Solvent : Buffer : Methanol : Acetonitrile λ_{max} : 223nm Range : 5-15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (C) & 20-60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (MS) Mobile Phase : Buffer pH 4.5: Methanol : Acetonitrile (50:25:25) Column : C ₁₈ Detector : LC 100 UV Flow rate : 1.0 ml/min	29
21.	Ravisankar P, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Atenolol, Hydrochlorothiazide, Amlodipine and Nebivolol	RP HPLC	Solvent: Phosphate buffer: Acetonitrile λ_{max} : 235nm Range : 2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (MS) Mobile Phase : 10 mM Phosphate buffer (pH3.0) : Acetonitrile (50:50 v/v) Flow rate: 1ml/min Run time: 2min	30
22.	Nalluri BN, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Telmisartan In Bulk And Pharmaceutic al Dosage Forms	RP-HPLC	Solvent: Methanol λ_{max} : 230nm Range : 5-25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (MS) & 2-10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (TEL) Mobile Phase : 15mM Ammonium acetate (pH 6.5): Acetonitrile (58:42) Column: C ₁₈ Detector: SPD-M20A PDA Run time: 3.9 min(M), 5.3 min(T)	31
23.	Thakkar NM, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Olmesartan Medoxomil in pharmaceutical dosage form	Stability indicating RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation	Solvent : Acetonitrile : Water λ_{max} : 220nm Range : 5-35 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Mobile Phase : 0.05% Trifluoro acetic acid (TFA): Acetonitrile (70 : 30 v/v) Column: YMC-Pack CN Detector: UV/VIS PDA Flow rate: 1ml/min Run time: 7 min	32
24.	Rao LA, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Amlodipine In Bulk Drug And Pharmaceutical Formulations	Stability Indicating HPLC	Solvent : Buffer, Acetonitrile λ_{max} : 237nm Range : 10-50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (AD) & 40-200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (M) Mobile Phase : Acetonitrile : Potassium dihydrogen	33

				phosphate buffer adjusted to pH 3.0 (50:50, v/v) Column: RP C ₁₈ ace-EPS Detector: UV Flow rate: 0.6ml/min	
25.	Baldania SL, et al	Metoprolol succinate & Olmesartan Medoxomilin Pharmaceutical Formulation	Thin-Layer Chromatographic-Densitometric	Solvent : Methanol λ_{\max} : 224nm Range :1000–2250 ng per spot (MS) & 800–1800 ng per spot (OM) Mobile Phase : Methanol : Ethyl acetate : Toluene : Glacial acetic acid (2.5 : 3 : 4.5 : 0.3V/V) Stationary Phase : silica gel G 60 F254	34
26.	Jain N, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Telmisartan in Bulk Drug and Their Dosage Forms	RP-HPLC	Solvent : Acetonitrile : Methanol : Phosphate buffer λ_{\max} : 225nm Range : 5-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (M) & 8-40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (T) Mobile Phase : Acetonitrile : Methanol : Phosphate buffer pH-5 (35:35:30 v/v/v) Column : Prontosil C ₁₈ Flow rate : 1ml/min Run time : 2.57 min (M) & 4.68 min (T)	35
27.	Raval M, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Olmesartan Medoxomil in Tablet Dosage	RP-HPLC	Solvent: Methanol: Water: CAN λ_{\max} : 231nm Range: 5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (M) & 2-12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (OM) Mobile Phase : Methanol: Water: Acetonitrile (70: 20 : 10) Column: Hibar 250-4.6 C ₁₈ Flow rate: 1ml/min Run time: 2.1 min (MS) 3.0 min (OM)	36
28.	Deshpande PB, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Olmesartan in Combined Capsule Dosage Form	HPTLC	Solvent : Methanol λ_{\max} : 225nm Range : 250-2500 ng band ⁻¹ (MS) & 100-1000 ng band ⁻¹ Mobile Phase : n- butanol : Methanol (6:3, v/v)	37
29.	Nawale PS, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Telmisartan in Pharmaceutical	(1) Normal (2) Reversed- Phase HPTLC	Solvent: Methanol λ_{\max} : 242nm Mobile Phase : (1) Toluene :	38

		Formulation		Propanol : Methanol : triethylamine (8:1:1:0.5 v/v) (2) Methanol: Water : Triethylamine (6:4:0.5 v/v) Column:(1) silica gel 60F ₂₅₄ S (2) Aluminium coated with RP-18 silica gel 60 F ₂₅₄ S	
30.	Patel MM, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Olmesartan Medoxomil in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form	RP-HPLC	Solvent : Methanol λ_{max} : 220nm Mobile Phase : Buffer (2 ml O-phosphoric acid in 2000 ml milli-Q Water) & Acetonitrile 50:50 (v/v) Column : inertsil ODS 3V Detector : PDA Flow rate : 1min/min Run time: 1.6 min(M) & 2.4 min (OM)	39
31.	Phale MD, et al.	Metoprolol succinate from Bulk Drugs	RP HPLC	Solvent: Methanol λ_{max} : 254nm Column: RP Spherisorb C ₁₈ Flow rate: 1ml/min Run time: 5min	40
32.	Ghosh SK, et al.	Metoprolol succinate & Hydrochlorothiazide in a Tablet Formulation	RP- HPLC	Solvent : 50mM di-sodium hydrogen phosphate : Methanol : Acetonitrile λ_{max} : 222nm Range : 2.0, 4.0, 8.0, 16.0, 32.0 ppm Mobile Phase : 50mM di-sod. hydrogen phosphate: Methanol : Acetonitrile	41

Table 3 Reported methods for assessment of Empagliflozin

Sr. No.	Author	Title	Description	Ref No
1.	Gaikwad, Asmita V., and Preeti Khulbe	HPLC Method Development for the Estimation of Empagliflozin in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Formulation	Mobile Phase: Water: CAN (55:45 v/v) Column: Waters C-18, 100 x 4.6 mm, 2.7 um, Poroshell 120 EC-C18 Detection: 225nm	42
2.	Sushil D. Patil, Sayali K. Chaurse, Maswood Ahmed Hafizur Rahman, Prajktta U. Varpe, Sanjay Kshirsagar	Development and Validation of Simple UV- Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Empagliflozin	Solvent: water: methanol (9.0:1.0) Λ_{max} : 224 nm	43
3.	Manojkumar K. Munde, Nilesh S. Kulkarni, Rahul H. Khiste, Dhanya B. Sen	Development and Validation of Novel Analytical Method for Empagliflozin and Metformin Hydrochloride in Bulk and	Detection WL: 224 and 232 nm	44

		Pharmaceutical Dosage Form by Four Different Simultaneous Estimation Approaches using UV Spectroscopy		
4.	Vaishali M. Badgujar, Pritam S. Jain	Stability-Indicating RP-HPLC Method Development for the Determination of Empagliflozin	Agilent C18 column (5µm; 4.6 x 250 mm) Mobile phase: methanol/ 0.05% pH 3.3 acetic acid (75:25) Stability: Oxidative stress and exposure to water caused relatively higher degradation	45
5.	Madure V, Barge V.	Analytical Method Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method For Estimation of Empagliflozin in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form.	Mobile phase: mixture of 0.1 % Trifluoroacetic acid in Water and Methanol Column: Phenomenex C-18, 250 mm X 4.6 mm, 5 µm	46
6.	Joanna Wittckind Manoel	Determination of empagliflozin in the presence of its organic impurities and identification of two degradation products using UHPLC-QTOF/MS	Instrument: UHPLC equipment (Shimadzu-Nexera x2), Zorbax Eclipse Plus Column: C18 column (2.1 × 50 mm, 1.8 µm) Temperature: 35 °C	47
7.	Juveriya Fatima Siddiqui	Analytical Method Development and Validation for Simultaneous Estimation of Empagliflozin and Linagliptin in Bulk Drug and in Pharmaceutical Dosage Formulation by HPLC	Column: waters acquity C18 (100 X 2.1mm id) Retention time: 1.320 and 2.343 min Wavelength: 270nm	48
8.	Yogeshwari Jambhulkar I, Nitu Madan and Pratik Mate	EMPAGLIFLOZIN: RP-HPLC BASED ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION	Column: C18 Mobile phase: 0.1% trifluoroacetic acid: acetonitrile 70:30 (v/v) pH 4.8	49
9.	Avinash C, Gandhimathi R.	RP-HPLC Method Development and Validation for an Estimation of Empagliflozin from Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form	Column: Agilent Eclipse XDE C-18 (4.6 mm x 250 mm, 5.0 µm particle size) Mobile phase: 0.1 M TEA pH 5.5 corrected by methanol and OPA in a proportion of 4:96 percent v/v Wavelength: 270 nm	50
10.	Pathak, S., Mishra, P	Stability-indicating HPLC-DAD method for the determination of empagliflozin	Detector: DAD Mobile phase: methanol/ acetonitrile/ 0.1% OPA (75:20:5) Retention time: 2.54 min	51
11.	N. Padmaja and G. Veerabhadram	Development and validation of analytical method for Simultaneous estimation of Empagliflozin and Linagliptin in bulk drugs and combined dosage forms using UV-visible spectroscopy	Vierodt's Method WL: 233nm and 277nm concentration range: 5-15µg/ml Solvent: Methanol	52

12.	A. Raja Reddy, J.Lavanya, T. Rama Rao , B. Revathi	analytical method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of metformin and empagliflozin in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form by RP-HPLC	Column: C18 150 mm I.D × 4.6 mm, 5 μm Mobile phase: 0.1N Potassium dihydrogen phosphate: Acetonitrile (50:50) Wavelength: 260nm	53
13.	Abhijeet N. Raut, Shailesh G. Jawarkar, Vaibhav S. Khodke, Vivek A. Khole	method development, validation by simultaneous estimation of empagliflozin and linagliptin by RP-HPLC method	Column: C18 (Equisil BDS) column (4.6 × 250 mm) 5μ Mobile phase: (40:60 v/v) methanol: water Instrument: SHIMADZU-HPLC system Pump -HPD 20A Detector - UV detector Software - UV Probe	54
14.	Chandni Chandarana, Aarti Panchal, Vishal Modi	RP-HPLC Method Validation for Estimation of related Substances of Empagliflozin	Mobile phase: Water:ACN Column: Phenomenex (Kinetex) C18 stationary phase (250mm × 4.6mm, particle size 5μm) Detection : 240nm	55
15.	Dr. K M Khairul Alam1,* Tanbin Jahan Ferdousy	Development and Validation of an RP-HPLC Method for Determination of Empagliflozin in Empagliflozin Tablet	Column: C18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size) Mobile phase: 0.01 M NaH ₂ PO ₄ (as buffer) and acetonitrile WL: 210nm	56
16.	Mounika P Siridevi, Hemant T Kumar, Srinivasa Y Rao, Vara Prasad K Rao.	RP-HPLC Method for Quantification of Empagliflozin in Pharmaceutical Formulation.	Column: C18G (250 x 4.6 mm i.d., 5μ) Mobile phase: methanol and water in the ratio of 70:30 % v/v WL: 233nm	57

Table 4 Reported methods for assessment of Metoprolol succinate and Empagliflozin in combination

Sr. No.	Author	Title	Description	Ref. No
1	Heena Ninama, Shaileshkumar K. Koradia	RP-HPLC Based Concurrent Analysis of Empagliflozin and Metoprolol Succinate in a Novel Pharmaceutical Combination Tablet	Column: Shim-pack ODS C18 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm I.D., 5 μm) Mobile Phase: potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 3.5) methanol, and acetonitrile in a 45:20:35 % (v/v/v) WL: 222nm Retention time: 8.217 min	58
2	Heena Ninama, Shaileshkumar K Koradia	Greenness assessment and stability- indicating HPTLC method for the concurrent analysis of empagliflozin and metoprolol succinate in a novel combined oral formulation	Stationary Phase: HPTLC silica gel 60 F254 plates Mobile Phase: chloroform: methanol: toluene (3.0:2.5:4.5, v/v/v) Detection: 222nm	59
3	Vandit Patel , Riddhi Trivedi, Munshi	Stability Indicating Method Development and Validation of	Column: C18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	60

	Mahammed Tanzil , Deepa R. Patel	Metoprolol Succinate and Empagliflozin by RP-HPLC in Synthetic Mixture	Mobile phase: acetonitrile and phosphate buffer (pH 4.0) in the ratio of 60:40 v/v Detection: 225nm	
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CONCLUSION:

This review article presents the Physicochemical properties and Pharmacological actions of Metoprolol succinate and Empagliflozin. The presented review gives information about the various methods reported in the literature for determining Metoprolol succinate and Empagliflozin, including official pharmacopeial assay methods.

This review concluded that different analytical methods are reported for the estimation of Metoprolol succinate and Empagliflozin individually and other combinations like UV Spectroscopy, HPLC, HPTLC, and LC-MS. Hence, all methods were simple, accurate, precise, and reproducible. The Literature review focuses on various UV methods reported for Metoprolol succinate and Empagliflozin in fixed-dose combinations. This review will help develop the analytical methods for this new combination and give knowledge about both drugs' characteristics.

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